

Sinitsyn I., Sizonenko V. Examples of mitigating the effects of radioactive contamination inputs by changing nuclear power plant regimes (France) and water body regimes (Ukraine)

Under conditions of military operations on the territory of Ukraine, the probability of damage to nuclear facilities is increasing; therefore, rapid and accurate determination of pollutant concentrations and application of water protection actions, especially under conditions of limited data at key points - water intakes, large cities, etc., are of particular relevance.

The UNDBE model, which, unlike widespread models that traditionally use advection dispersion equations (ADE), actually uses the aggregated dead zone (ADZ) method. Instead of modeling the solution concentration continuously over both distance and time, the ADZ model uses a "black box" approach and simply considers the concentration at the outlet of the chamber as a function of the input concentration and time. The ADZ model requires significantly fewer initial data and provides a sharp reduction in the required computer time while maintaining accuracy within the existing measurement errors. When using the proposed model, it will be necessary to determine its parameters. These parameters are determined by parametric identification from the measurement data. It was shown that the accuracy of the calculations corresponds to the measurement errors both in terms of pollution concentrations and the moments of its arrival.

The model was tested in the international EMRAS project [1]. The modeling of the transfer of radioactive ^3H emissions from 5 NPPs (14 nuclear reactors) in the 350-kilometer channel of the Loire River for six months. It was necessary to determine the dynamics of ^3H concentrations at 11 sites with a time resolution one hour. To apply the model, the Loire River section was divided into 33 consecutive chambers. Solving the problem of ^3H transport using the proposed UNDBE model takes 8 seconds with an Intel Core i5-9600K processor. As the modeling results show (Fig. 1), the maximum ^3H concentrations in the Loire River waters (109 Bq/l) during the period under consideration were observed in Nouan downstream of RejetStLaurent NPP on 01.10.1999. This situation resulted from the interference of ^3H releases from RejetStLaurent NPP and releases from RejetBelleville and RejetDampierre NPPs upstream.

Fig. 1 Interference of Belleville, Dampierre and St-Laurent NPP emissions

The situation was modeled in which the ^3H release from RejetStLaurent NPP (kBq/sec), which took place on 01.10.1999, entered the aquatic environment 32 hours later than in reality without changing its intensity and duration. At the same time, there was no interference of this release with the releases of overlying NPPs.

The modeling results (Fig. 2) show a significant (35%) decrease in the amplitude value of radionuclide concentration in water in Nouan (70 Bq/l). Thus, it is shown that it is possible to reduce the amplitude values of radioactive contamination concentrations by changing the NPP emission regime without reducing the amount of discharged contamination.

Fig. 2 Interference of Belleville, Dampierre and St-Laurent NPP emissions after changing emission regime of St-Laurent NPP

Modeling of ^{90}Sr transportation through the Kiev reservoir (length 110 km, volume 3 km^3) showed that increasing the time of water mass transportation and reservoir volume significantly reduces the concentration amplitude at the reservoir outflow (city Kiev water intake site). This is mainly due to an increase in the dispersion of pollution in the reservoir volume. This can be used as a water protection measure by changing the HPP regime, and the model will give an opportunity to quickly assess the possible result depending on specific conditions. On the example of modeling of ^{90}Sr release passage in 1991 the possibility of 20% reduction of ^{90}Sr amplitude concentration is shown. Time of calculation one-year interval for 6 reservoirs less 0.1 sec.

One of main mining objects of the city Krivoy Rog is a mine «Nova», which works mine of ferrous and uranium ores. Mine water that is pumped out is saturated with uranium waste flows into the Zoltaya River. This in the turn, results in contamination of waters of Ingulets River and Karachunovskoe reservoir - basic source of water-supply of whole region. Protection action is dilution by waters from the storage pool

of Ingulets River. Such measures in many cases enable to access to safe and adequate water supply during the catastrophic events. The new model gave the opportunity to count different scenarios of water discharge from storage pool of Ingulets River fast and find time and minimal water discharge for decreasing concentration below maximum concentration limit.

Uses simple software that allows the use of a laptop computer and fast determinations can be made “in situ” and in real time.

- Testing of Models for Predicting the Behaviour of Radionuclides in Freshwater Systems and Coastal Areas. <http://www-ns.iaea.org/downloads/rw/projects/emras/final-reports/aquatic-tecdoc-final.pdf>